

INTERACTION OF RUBBER AND CARBON TETRACHLORIDE

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A mechanism for the evolution of hydrogen chloride due to interaction of rubber and carbon tetrachloride, when brought together in direct sunlight, diffused daylight or to radiations of wave-lengths about and below $5200\text{\AA}$, is suggested

Carbon tetrachloride has been used for studies on the solution properties of natural rubber. It has been tacitly assumed that no chemical reaction between the two takes place; but carbon tetrachloride has been found to show a negative heat of mixing with natural rubber. There is absorption of heat (0.37-1.36 cal./g.) with benzene, dichloroethylene and toluene, while there is evolution of heat (2-3 cal./g.) with carbon tetrachloride and chloroform (Hock and Schmidt, *Rubber Chem. Tech.*, 1934, 7, 462; cf. "Advances in Colloid Science", Vol. II, Interscience, 1946, p. 155). There is considerable evolution of heat ("Natural & Synthetic High Polymers", Vol. IV, Interscience, 1950, p. 704) on mixing cellulose triacetate with tetrachloroethane and the solvent is found to be completely bound with the polymer. It appears therefore that similar combination between rubber and carbon tetrachloride may occur, when these are brought together. An indication of chemical interaction of carbon tetrachloride and rubber has been found in an examination of the spectra of carbon tetrachloride solutions of natural rubber (Dasgupta, Ramakrishnan and Pande, *J. Polymer Sci.*, 1955, 17, 255). Chemical analysis of rubber, aged in solution at the laboratory temperature, showed that chlorine was incorporated into the rubber.

In the present investigation a progressive detailed study of the system of deproteinised rubber-carbon tetrachloride has been carried out from the instant the two are brought in contact till either a homogeneous solution (in darkness only) or a gel is obtained (visible radiations).

EXPERIMENTAL

Deproteinised natural rubber (about 0.2 g.) was accurately weighed. An amount of CCl_4 that would furnish a 2% (w/v) solution was taken in a pyrex tube (20 c.c.) having a ground-glass joint. The weighed rubber was added under the conditions of experiment and the tube closed with another pyrex tube (20 c.c.) with a reciprocal ground-glass joint. The opposite end of this second tube had earlier been drawn out into a capillary and sealed. For the experiments with diffused daylight and direct sunlight, the tubes were exposed on racks. In experiments with different wave-lengths of light, the tubes were mounted on a water-cooled panel opposite 'Baker' $2'' \times 2''$ filters and placed about 10'' away and equidistant from a 200 watt clear tungsten lamp. Experiments were also carried out in which samples were mixed and kept in complete darkness.

After the exposure, the capillary was broken under water, when water rushed into the tubes. The contents of the tubes were refluxed for fifteen minutes and the hydrogen chloride determined. The chlorine content of the rubber left from refluxing was determined after precipitation with methyl alcohol, followed by solution in benzene and reprecipitation with methyl alcohol.

TABLE I

A. Direct sunlight in pyrex tube.								
Exposed for (in hrs.)	...	12	24	48	60	96	168	1980
% Free HCl on wt. of rubber	...	0.4	1.4	1.5	2.2	2.4	3.3	7.1
% Cl content of the rubber	...	1.5	3.3	4.3	6.7	...	9.12	31.0
B. Diffused daylight in pyrex tube.								
Exposed for (in hrs.)	...	12	24	36	84	108		
% Free HCl on wt. of rubber	...	0.2	0.3	0.6	0.9	1.2		
% Cl content of rubber	...	1.3	1.2	2.0	2.8	3.94		

TABLE II

Nature of tube.	Time of exposure.	Nature of exposure.	% Free HCl on wt. of rubber.	% Cl content of the rubber.
Pyrex	96 hrs.	Red filter, 6500Å	0.0	0.0
"	96	Yellow filter 5800Å	0.0	0.0
"	96	Dark green filter 5200Å	0.0096	0.0
"	96	Dark blue, 4700Å	0.076	0.71
Quartz	15½	U.V. 3600Å	0.69	2.5
"	36	U.V. 3600Å	1.59	6.5

DISCUSSION

It is observed (Table I) that evolution of HCl progressively increases and attains a value of 7% in 1980 hours of exposure in direct sunlight; exposure to diffused daylight also gives off HCl which attains a value of 1.2% in 108 hours. There is a simultaneous incorporation of chlorine as well. It has been found possible to attain as high a chlorine content as 31% on prolonged exposure to sunlight.

Table II shows that hydrogen chloride is evolved when the samples are exposed to radiations of wave-lengths about and below 5200Å, chlorination of rubber also taking place simultaneously. Such reactions also take place when rubber—CCl₄ systems are exposed in a quartz tube to U.V. radiation (3600Å).

In samples which were mixed and kept in complete darkness there was no hydrogen chloride evolution.

These results show that CCl₄—rubber systems progressively pass on into partially chlorinated rubber—CCl₄ systems, with evolution of HCl unless they are kept in complete darkness or exposed only to light of wave-lengths above 5200Å.

This observation throws doubt on the validity of the results of solution properties of rubber- CCl_4 systems, reported in literature, since a part of the rubber would have changed into chlorinated rubber. Hock and Schmidt (*loc. cit.*) observed a negative heat of solution when rubber was dissolved in CCl_4 . The evolution of HCl during this dissolution process explains this negative heat of solution.

Kharasch, Jensen and Urry (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, **69**, 1100) have shown that mono-olefins, such as octene-1, react with CCl_4 only in presence of peroxides or ultraviolet light, these being responsible for the splitting of CCl_4 into radicals. They do not report the evolution of HCl by a substitutive attack of the free radicals on the olefin. The absence of a chemical reaction between rubber and CCl_4 in the dark suggests that peroxidic centres, even if present in unmastered deproteinised rubber, are not responsible for this reaction. Bateman (*J. Polymer Sci.*, 1947, **2**, 1) has shown that photodecomposition of natural rubber takes place only when rubber is irradiated with ultraviolet light. That photodissociation of CCl_4 does not take place with visible radiation can be judged from the fact that its absorption continuum has been reported to be in the ultraviolet region (2800 Å to 2700 Å) (Saha, *Bull. Acad. Sci.*, U.P., 1933, **2**, 233; Lowry and Sass, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 622). The fact that hydrogen chloride is evolved under conditions, which normally exclude the decomposition of either rubber or CCl_4 , suggests that rubber- CCl_4 systems give rise to hydrogen chloride and chlorinated rubber even at lower energy levels by absorption of light of wave-lengths between 3000 Å and 5200 Å. Results in Table II indicate that at energy levels lower than that corresponding to 5200 Å no chemical change takes place, as revealed by the absence of HCl.

The following explanations are offered for the observations on the interaction of rubber and CCl_4 even with radiations of longer wave-length.

Transference of high energy through macro-molecules has been suggested by Alexander and Charlesby (*Nature*, 1954, **173**, 4404, 578) to explain the particular behaviour of various polymers under the action of high energy radiation. In the present investigation reactions requiring normally a higher energy, viz., photodecomposition of either rubber or carbon tetrachloride to furnish radicals, are brought about in this macromolecular system by the absorption and transference of lower energies.

From an examination of the infra-red spectrum of CCl_4 solutions of natural rubber (*loc. cit.*) it has been postulated that a complex is formed between the two. It is also possible that even the low energies corresponding to 5200 Å, absorbed in various parts of the rubber chain, result in the decomposition of the complex to provide radicals, which then chlorinate the rubber and at the same time, to some extent, react substitutively, giving off hydrogen chloride.

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